

Some Anomalies between the Surfactants comprising Linear and Branched Hydrocarbon Chains

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This paper deals with the differences observed in the surface properties of two types of surfactant molecules of similar head groups and chain lengths of which one is comprised of linear alkyl chains and the other of branched hydrocarbon chains. The marked difference in the interfacial properties and liquid crystalline behaviour of these surfactants (viz. diethanolamine derivatives of n-alkyl as well as polyisobutylene succinic anhydride) are attributed to the conformational changes in the molecules caused by branching.

The comparison of refractive indices obtained by optical ellipsometry at the air-water interface showed negative anisotropy for the molecules with branched hydrocarbon chains during film compression which is in contrast to the molecules with linear alkyl chains. Similarly, the surface viscosity measured by deep channel surface viscometry showed that contrary to the surfactants with linear hydrocarbon chains, the monolayers of the surfactants with branched hydrocarbon chains were more liquid like. The surfactants with linear hydrocarbon chain exhibited increased viscosity in the presence of NaCl in the aqueous sub-phase whereas a significant drop in viscosity was observed with the surfactant comprising branched hydrocarbon chains. Similarly, a drop in viscosity was observed in the presence of ammonium nitrate. Such effects were reflected in the water evaporation rates through their monolayers.

Both of these surfactants formed lamellar liquid crystals alone and also with added water. The repeat distance between the layers of the liquid crystalline phase, measured by low angle X-ray diffraction (LAXD), differed significantly between the surfactants with linear and branched hydrocarbon chains. The repeat distance for a surfactant with a polyisobutylene hydrocarbon chain was higher than that of a surfactant with linear alkyl chain. Higher values of water penetration were observed in the hydrocarbon zone of lamellar liquid crystals of a surfactant comprising polyisobutylene chain.

In studies of the fundamental physicochemical properties of surface active agents, it is desirable to know the dimensions of the molecules, the manner in which they pack together in surface films, and the attractive and repulsive interactions between the individual molecules in the films. During the past two decades a wide range of studies has been carried out on surface active molecules with regard to the role of molecular structure, polar head groups and the influence of counterions on the polar head groups of surfactants in determining interfacial properties¹⁻⁶. However, little attention has been paid

to understanding the contribution or effect of the non-polar components of surface active molecules.

In recent years attention has been increasingly directed towards the phase properties of natural membranes to explain their structure and some of their functions. Lipid monolayers at the air/water interface have generated increasing interest as models of biological membranes, and also as models and precursors of well structured organic films. A recent study on lecithin molecules indicated that the isobranched lecithin differed primarily from the straight

chain lecithin in having a more expanded condensed state. This was attributed to impaired packing in the condensed state due to the methyl isobranched. Other studies of the non-polar group of amphiphilic molecules showed that the properties of fatty acids adsorbed at the interface in biological membranes are dependent partly on the lateral interactions between the adjacent chains. This leads to greater fluidity and permeability of surface films in membranes composed of such fatty acids⁷⁻¹⁰. A recent investigation of the interfacial properties of surfactants with branched hydrocarbon chains revealed some interesting differences between such surfactants and surfactants with linear alkyl chains. It was reported recently that the structure of the aliphatic chains of surfactants are equally important as their polar head groups in determining their properties and performances at different interfaces such as air-liquid, liquid-liquid and solid-liquid^{11,12}.

These findings seem to have provided the impetus for our recent series of investigations into the physical properties of surfactants of similar polar head groups containing linear and branched hydrocarbon chains. A significant contribution to the understanding of monolayers at the air-water interface has been made by the use of techniques such as fluorescence microscopy¹³, synchrotron X-ray reflectivity¹⁴, surface quasi-elastic light scattering¹⁵ and surface viscometry^{6,16}. However, little effort has been devoted to examining the relative differences in surface properties caused by altering the nature of hydrocarbon moiety in surfactants possessing similar polar head groups and hydrocarbon chain lengths. Here we present our most recent work on the interfacial characteristics of two molecules, having the same polar head group and chain length one of which has tetradecyl alkyl chains and the other one has branched hydrocarbon chains (polyisobutylene) of average backbone carbon number 14. The polar head groups are comprised of the diethanolamine derivative of succinic anhydride (Fig. 1). In order to investigate the influence of the hydrocarbon moiety on monomolecular films, we adopted the method of optical ellipsometry,

Fig. 1. Idealised molecular structure of surfactant comprising alkyl or polyisobutylene chain (*R*).

an appropriate and elegant tool for such studies on adsorbed monolayers at the air-water interface¹⁷⁻¹⁹. From this method valuable information concerning refractive index and film thickness can be obtained. Besides gaining information on optical and related properties, further insight into aspects relating to the structure, organisation and effect of branching on chain packing can be obtained from this method. The orientation of the adsorbed surfactant molecules, molecular interactions and packing, formation of complexes, or structural transformations at the interface can result in a great deal of variation in surface rheological properties. Interfacial viscosity provides valuable information about the nature of interactions, transport processes, and phase transitions in flowing monolayers which have been recognised as the primary factors in film transfer^{20,21}. It has been found that the monolayer property is profoundly affected by the hydrophobic and hydrophilic interactions^{22,23}. Of particular interest here is how the effect of branching causes differences in optical and rheological properties of surfactant monolayers. In this article we also introduce the observed differences in the liquid crystalline properties of these surfactants when the linear alkyl chain of the surfactant was replaced by a polyisobutylene chain. Significant changes in repeat distance and water penetration values were observed in the corresponding lamellar liquid crystals.

Results and Discussion

Optical and rheological properties of the monolayers :

Optical properties by ellipsometry measurements :
The experimental surface pressure and ellipsometric angle versus area (π -A and $\delta\Delta$ -A) isotherms of surfactants with alkyl chains and polyisobutylene chains are presented in Fig. 2. Surface pressure

Fig. 2. Comparative π - A and $-\delta\Delta$ - A isotherms of (1) DETA and (2) DEPA.

(π) and ellipsometric angles ($\delta\Delta$) were simultaneously recorded from the onset of detectable surface pressure. The method of optical ellipsometry is suitable for the investigation of adsorbed monolayers at the air-water interface and is an elegant tool with which to study the influence of hydrocarbon chains on monomolecular films. From this method valuable information concerning refractive index and film thickness can be obtained.

For a thin non-absorbing anisotropic film, the relevant ellipsometric parameter is $\delta\Delta$ ($\delta\Delta = \Delta - \bar{\Delta}$), where Δ is obtained in the presence of a film and $\bar{\Delta}$ in the absence of a film (water surface). The refractive index components and film thickness are related to $\delta\Delta$ by the following relationship¹⁷⁻¹⁹,

$$\delta\Delta = \Delta - \bar{\Delta} = - \left(\frac{4\pi d}{\lambda} \right) \left(\frac{\sin \phi_0 \tan \phi \sigma \nu_0 n_0}{1 - (n_0/n_2)^2 \tan^2 \phi_0} \right) \times \left[\frac{r_x^2 - r_z^2}{r_0^2 - r_z^2} \frac{r_0^2 (r_x^2 - r_z^2)}{r_z^2 (r_0^2 - r_z^2)} \right] \quad (1)$$

where λ is the wavelength of light, ϕ_0 the angle of incidence, n_0 and n_2 are respectively the refractive indices of the air and the substrate, d is the film thickness, n_x and n_z are respectively the perpendicular and parallel film refractive indices with respect

to the optical axis. A macroscopic model of a system consisting of a substance covered with a homogeneous monolayer is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Macroscopic model of a system comprising a substrate covered by a monolayer of thickness d ; n_0 , n_1 and n_2 are the refractive indices of air, substrate and monolayer respectively; n_x and n_z are the perpendicular and parallel refractive index components of the monolayer with respect to the optical axis.

As seen in equation (1), at a given angle of incidence (ϕ_0) and wavelength (λ) the ellipsometric angle $\delta\Delta$ is a function of three film parameters, viz. d , n_x and n_z . The unknown parameters (d , n_x and n_z) can not be determined solely from the measurement of $\delta\Delta$. For that matter one needs to develop a geometric model of the molecules that rationalises the experimental data and allows determination of the optical constant as a function of orientation of the surfactant molecules at the air-water interface. This can be achieved by means of a CPK atomic model which allows one to mimic the variation of the ellipsometric angles as a function of the molecular area during film compression^{18,19}. In the geometric model (Fig. 4) the acyl chain and the polar head group are included in a rectangular parallelepiped whose width and length are D_0 and D respectively. As seen in Fig. 4, the molecular area, film thickness and refractive indices can be varied with respect to the changes in angle of orientation (θ) of the surfactant molecule and can be described by the equations,

$$A = D_0^2 / (\cos \theta) \quad (2)$$

Fig 4 Rodlike model of the surfactant molecules. (D_0) diameter of the chain. (D_1) total length of the molecule. (D_2) length of the polar head group. (XYZ) coordinate axis and (θ) angle with respect to the vertical Z -axis

$$d = (D_1 - D_2 - D_0) \cos\theta + D_0 \quad (3)$$

$$n_x = \left[\frac{1}{2} (1 + \cos^2\theta) \epsilon_x + \epsilon_y \sin^2\theta \right]^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

$$n_z = (\epsilon_x \sin^2\theta + \epsilon_z \cos\theta)^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where ϵ_x and ϵ_z are the dielectric constants ($\epsilon = n^2$) of the film at $\theta = 0$.

By substituting equations (3), (4) and (5) in (1), $\delta\Delta$ can be obtained as a function of molecular area while D_0 , D_1 , D_2 , n_x and n_z are the parameters. These parameters can be determined by a program based on the least-squares method and n_x and n_z can be determined simultaneously via computer analysis as a function of θ for given molecular dimensions (D_0 , D_1 and D_2). While comparing surfactants of two different hydrocarbon chains, several points are apparent. (i) In contrast to the surfactants with alkyl chains the film collapse pressure of the surfactant with polyisobutylene chains is significantly lower. (ii) Higher film collapse pressure and the shape of the π -A isotherms of the surfactant with alkyl chains (DETA) suggest a more

condensed state of the film compared to the surfactant with polyisobutylene chains (DEPA). (iii) The ellipsometric angle $|\delta\Delta|$ of the surfactant with alkyl chains (DETA) increased upon compression and reached a steady state at the collapse pressure (a similar trend was observed with other surfactant systems)^{17a,17b}. However, for the surfactants with polyisobutylene chains (DEPA) the $\delta\Delta$ -A isotherm exhibited a sharper rise in $|\delta\Delta|$ in the close-packed region. (iv) The value of $|\delta\Delta|$ for the surfactant with polyisobutylene chains (DEPA) is significantly higher than that of the surfactant with alkyl chains (DETA).

In the close-packed state of the monolayer the molecular area of the surfactant DETA is found to be $21 \pm 1 \text{ \AA}^2$ for a surface pressure 48 mN m^{-1} . In a similar physical state, the molecular area of DEPA is $29.5 \pm 1 \text{ \AA}^2$ at a surface pressure 36 mN m^{-1} . By introducing $D_0 = 4.6$ for DETA and $D_0 = 5.43$ for DEPA for non-tilted hydrocarbon chains (according to equation 2), $D_1 = 29 \text{ \AA}$ (measured from CPK atomic models), and by assigning $D_2 = 12 \text{ \AA}$ for fully extended polar head groups, the optical parameters n_x and n_z can be calculated as a function of the angle of the orientation θ . In Figs. 5 and 6 the results of n_x and n_z calculated for DETA and DEPA are shown. At a detectable surface pressure, both the surfactants have an inclination of 65° and behave as isotropic media at an orientation of 55° . Upon compression of the monolayer the average area occupied by each surfactant decreases and as a consequence the acyl chains are lifted from the aqueous surface and stand parallel in an orientation perpendicular to the plane of the subphase.

In the case of DETA (Fig. 4) the results show normal behaviour, i.e. n_z increases with decreasing inclination of the molecules. Such changes in optical anisotropy upon film compression [$n_z < n_x$ (above 55°)] \rightarrow $n_z = n_x$ (at 55°) \rightarrow $n_z < n_x$ (below 55°)] indicate a regular shift from predominantly bent to upright orientation of the surfactant molecules. However, in the case of DEPA (n_x and

Fig. 5. Refractive index components n_x and n_z as a functional of orientation of DETA during film compression: (□) n_x and (●) n_z .

Fig. 6. Refractive index components n_x and n_z as a function of orientation of DEPA during film compression: (□) n_x and (●) n_z .

n_z are calculated at the same angle of orientation as that of DETA) the monolayer shows negative anisotropy [i.e. $n_z > n_x$ (above 55°) $\rightarrow n_z = n_x$ (at 55°) $\rightarrow n_z < n_x$ (below 55°)]. This strongly suggests that the films DETA and DEPA behave in a different manner. The change in ellipsometric

angle upon compression of the film is very sensitive to the nature of the hydrophobic environment of the surfactant molecules which seems to be of great importance in determining the molecular structure of the monolayers and their properties.

Despite having similar hydrocarbon chain length, the observed differences between DETA and DEPA also reveal that the changes in $|\delta\Delta|$ are more sensitive to the changes in refractive indices than the film thickness. The phase behaviour of monolayers at relatively higher surface density is strongly influenced by the packing of the hydrocarbon chains and our results reveal that branched hydrocarbon chains do not pack in a similar way to that of alkyl ones²⁴.

The branching in alkyl chains (viz. methyl substitution in polyisobutylene chains in DEPA) causes a lowering of the collapse pressure. It is well known that branched chains have weaker intermolecular cohesive forces than straight chain ones^{7,10}. The weaker attractive forces in the hydrocarbon region cause perturbation in chain packing. The presence of a large number of methyl substituents on the polyisobutylene chains restricts the rotational degrees of freedom around C-C bond which causes the chains to tilt and prevent them from packing in a close manner^{10,26}. The negative optical birefringence observed with the monolayers of DEPA can be attributed to a conformational defect which occurs at the level of the chains. Such a defect can alter the molecular polarisability to a large extent. The positive anisotropy observed with DETA is due to the fact that polarisability acting along the molecular axis of the surfactant is greater than that acting perpendicularly to the molecular axis. A schematic presentation of such behaviour is shown in Fig. 7. Therefore, it is possible that the molecules of DEPA at the air-water interface have reduced polarisability (acting along the molecular axis) due to their bent conformation^{18,19,25,26} which in turn influences the changes in refractive indices during film compression.

The influence of such hydrophobic interactions

Fig. 7. Schematic representation of molecular conformation and its effect on polarisability acting along the molecular axis (Z).

in monomolecular films was further investigated by surface viscosity measurements.

Surface viscosity by deep channel surface viscometry: Recent studies by Hühnerfus *et al.* delineate the optimum hydrophobic interactions between the alkyl chains that result in an increase in surface viscosity^{22,23}. In our study we have carried out surface viscosity measurements by deep channel viscometry on the monolayers of DETA and DEPA and compared the influence of salts, viz. NaCl and AN. In our previous studies we examined the effect of salt concentration on surface viscosity⁶. The experiments on the surfactants with different alkyl chain length showed that irrespective of the chain length, the film viscosity increases with increased concentration of sodium chloride whereas a reverse trend was observed with AN in the aqueous sub-phase. Such differences in viscosity behaviour were mainly due to the changes in the environments of the polar head group regions imposed by the nature of salts.

Upon comparing the surfactants DETA and DEPA, of similar chain length, the results turned out to be very interesting and supported the phenomena observed in ellipsometric studies. Before discussing

the results on surface viscosity it is worthwhile to discuss the technic in brief. In a deep channel surface viscometer (Fig. 8) the channel walls are

Fig. 8. Schematic diagram of the deep channel viscometer.

stationary concentric cylinders; the floor of the viscometer moves with a constant angular velocity. In order to estimate the centre-line velocity of the interface containing surfactant film, the velocity of a Teflon particle carefully placed at the surface of the liquid in the annular channel is measured. From the measured rotational velocity of the particle (V), the interfacial viscosity (ϵ) at the air-water interface can be expressed by equation⁶,

$$\epsilon = \frac{ny_0}{\pi} \left[\frac{8V_b}{\pi V e^{\pi D}} - 1 \right] \quad (6)$$

where n is bulk viscosity of the sub-phase, y_0 the channel width, V_b the plate rotational speed and D the ratio of depth to width of the liquid channel. For the present study each experiment was repeated at least five times and the average velocity of the particle was used for calculating surface viscosity. The plate rotational speed of 4.6 rpm was used for all experiments.

The surface viscosity datum for each surfactant system was expressed as a dimensionless Boussinesq number, ϵ/ny_0 , and the plots of $\ln \epsilon/ny_0$ versus molecular surface area of the surfactants are shown

in Fig. 9. In all our experiments surface viscosities

Fig. 9. Plot of $\ln \epsilon/\eta_0$ versus molecular surface area of DETA and DEPA at water, 20% NaCl and 20% AN solution substrates: (—) DETA–water, (○) DETA–20% NaCl, (□) DETA–20% AN, (---) DEPA–water, (●) DEPA–20% NaCl and (■) DEPA–20% AN.

were measured below the film collapse pressures of the monomolecular films of the surfactants. The corresponding pressure-area isotherms of DETA and DEPA in the presence of NaCl and AN in the aqueous substrate are also shown in Fig. 10.

In Fig. 9, the differences between the monolayers of DETA and DEPA are quite conspicuous. In the case of DETA the presence of NaCl favours the formation of a highly viscous 'solid-like' film due to the strong hydrophobic cohesion²⁸ that results from the salting-out effect at the interface, whereas the presence of AN leads to the formation of low viscosity liquidlike films due to the salting-in effect. Such effects have been discussed in detail in our previous reports^{6,27}. However, in the case of DEPA, regardless of the nature of the salts present in the aqueous sub-phase it produced low viscosity liquid-like films. The reason for such behaviour of surface viscosity can be further considered in conjunction with the pressure-area isotherms of

DETA and DEPA (Fig. 10, Table 1). The main distinguishable features are as follows. (i) At low surface pressures the monolayer of DEPA is more expanded than that of DETA in both NaCl and AN solution substrates. (ii) The DETA film collapse pressure increases in the presence of NaCl and AN in the aqueous sub-phase (such an increase is more pronounced with NaCl compared to AN), whereas irrespective of the nature of the salt the film collapse pressure of DEPA decreases. (iii) The slopes of the pressure-area isotherms near collapse pressure are higher for DETA, indicating less fluidity and higher stability of the DETA surface films compared to DEPA.

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF MONOLAYER PROPERTIES OF DETA AND DEPA

Parameter	DETA			DEPA		
	Water	20%NaCl	20%AN	Water	20%NaCl	20%AN
Collapse pressures (mN/m)	48	52	49	36	32	30
Area/molecule at collapse (\AA^2)	21±1	25±1	28±1	29.5±1	33±1	38±1
Area/molecule at the condensed state (\AA^2)	33±1	37±1	38±1	46±	±2	63±2
Rate of water evaporation ($\text{g/cm}^2/\text{min}$) × 10 ⁴ measured at 13 mN/m	—	4.1	5.8	—	5.8	6.8

The anomalous viscosity behaviour of DEPA appears to be caused by the weaker cohesion as opposed to the potential hydrophobic cohesion observed with DETA which mainly originates from the packing defect caused by branching in the hydrocarbon chains as discussed in the previous section.

The conclusions were further supported by the experimental evidence on the rate of evaporation of water from the monomolecular films of DETA and DEPA in the presence of NaCl and AN solution substrates. The surfactant spread on a Langmuir trough was compressed to a certain molecular area. A known amount of pre-dried CaCl_2 was kept above the monolayer. The weight gained by CaCl_2 due to water absorption from evaporation was measured after 5 min²⁹. The results (Table 1) showed that the rate of evaporation of water through the monolayer of DEPA is significantly higher than

Fig. 10. π - A isotherms of DETA and DEPA at (1) water, (2) 20% NaCl and (3) 20% AN solution substrates.

that of DETA. This indicates that the DETA molecules are well oriented and exert stronger cohesive interactions between the hydrocarbon chains which result in the formation of more compact films compared to DEPA.

In our earlier studies, infrared spectroscopy on Langmuir-Blodgett films of the DEPA type molecules indicated the presence of *gauche* conformations in the hydrocarbon chains⁴. The conformational defects that occur mainly at the end of the hydrocarbon chains^{30,32}, vary in a random manner in the monolayer. This may cause the chains to push apart and result in the formation of liquid-like films due to the loss of film organisation caused by branching.

Liquid crystals : The differences in the behaviour of surfactants comprising linear and branched hydrocarbon chains were further studied in their lamellar liquid crystalline phases. It is worthwhile

to mention in this regard that qualitatively one can predict about the type of liquid-crystal phase occurred in any system by a consideration of three properties : (i) charge, (ii) alkyl chain/water interactions and (iii) molecular shape. Molecular shape affects the way molecules pack into lamellar or hexagonal aggregates. It is easier to pack molecules having a bulky head group (wedge-shaped) into hexagonal phase, while surfactants having bulkier hydrocarbon chains (e.g. phospholipids) fit into lamellar structure. In this section the comparisons are made between the surfactants DEPA and diethanolamine derivative of dodecyl succinic anhydride (DEDA). The reason for comparing DEDA instead of DETA is due to the fact that DETA is crystalline in nature and does not entrain water. In our previous studies it was shown that both DEDA and DETA follow similar trends of results^{6,18,19}. Therefore in order to investigate the differences between the surfactants with linear and branched

hydrocarbon chains, the study of DEDA and DEPA in their liquid crystalline phases should provide a meaningful comparison.

In the lamellar liquid crystalline phases of DEDA and DEPA, the repeat distances were measured by LAXD and the results are shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Interlayer spacings of lamellar liquid crystals of DEDA and DEPA measured by LAXD : (□) DEDA and (○) DEPA.

A linear dependence between the water to surfactant volume ratio (R) and the repeat distance (d) was observed for both the surfactants. The variation in d values of DEDA occurred between 32–45 Å whereas DEPA gave an initial value of 51.5 Å and increased up to 71 Å in the presence of larger amounts of water. The increase in d value with increased water content signifies the degree to which the water penetrates the hydrocarbon chain region of the lamellar liquid crystals. From the measured d values it is possible to calculate the fraction of water penetrating the hydrocarbon chain region by considering the following relationship :

$$d = d_0(1 + R)/(1 + \alpha R) \quad (7)$$

in which d_0 is the interlayer spacing at zero solvent content and α is the volume fraction of water penetration in the hydrocarbon chain region³³. Some typical values of α obtained from the experimental results (Fig. 10) are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2 —INTERLAYER SPACINGS AND PENETRATION VALUES

Surfactant	R	d	α
DEDA	0	32.0	—
	0.050	33.7	0.06
	0.199	38.1	0.04
	0.394	43.8	0.05
DEPA	0	51.5	—
	0.050	54.0	0.22
	0.170	57.1	0.39
	0.350	60.0	0.49

From the d values one can obtain significant information about the structures present. The interlayer spacings without water may be compared to the length of fully extended hydrocarbon chains. Hence, the chains of DEDA molecules in fully extended form should have a repeat distance of 43 Å instead of 32 Å. The experimental result of 32 Å indicates a considerable disorder of the molecular conformation. By considering the polar head group structure of DEDA, it is reasonable to attribute the disorder to the change in head group conformation. The earlier investigation³³ by infrared spectroscopy on similar kind of molecules virtually ruled out the possibility of parallel packing of the fully stretched head groups in the lamellar liquid crystalline phase. The study indicated that the head groups are present in a zwitterionic state (Fig. 1). The absence of any intermolecularly hydrogen bonded dimers in these molecules and indications about the presence of hydrogen bonds involving $-\text{NH}-$ and $-\text{OH}-$ from a carboxylic group as well as $-\text{NH}_2-$ and ionised carboxylic acid group suggest a coiled conformation of the polar head group (Fig. 12a). Such conformation permits the $-\text{NH}-$ group to be adjacent to the ionised and nonionised carboxylate group and increases the head group cross-sectional area almost double of the hydrocarbon chain that leads to a pronounced reduction of the chain order. The addition of water relaxes the strong hydrogen bonds between the ionised carboxylate group, the carboxylic acid group and iminium ion³⁴ which results in a conformational change of DEDA from curled to the linear conformation (Fig. 12b). The repeat distance value of 45 Å at a higher water content explains the

Fig 12. (a) Conformation of DEDA with head group curled, (b) linear conformation of DEDA and (c) liquid crystalline packing conformation of DEPA

reduced disorder of DEDA molecules where the area per head group is reduced upon the conformational change.

Contrary to DEDA, the value of repeat distance of DEPA was higher. An experimental interlayer spacing of 51.5 Å seems to be a reasonable value for an extended molecular conformation of DEPA^{18,19} as shown in Fig. 12c. However, from the CPK model of a fully stretched DEPA molecule (as shown in Fig. 4) the ideal value should be 58 Å ($2D_1$), a 12% reduction in repeat distance value can be attributed to the bent conformation of the polyisobutylene chain. The results reveal that the presence of a bulkier polyisobutylene chain in DEPA reduces the possibility of head group coiling and this can further be favoured by increased distance of separation between the adjacent head groups. A bent conformation of the polyisobutylene chain makes it even more difficult for the head groups to interact. The result of water penetration in the hydrocarbon zone (Fig. 13) of DEPA appears justified which can be concluded as a consequence of no

Fig. 13 General view of a lamellar liquid crystal (A) layers of water molecules and polar head groups, (B) hydrocarbon chains and (C) methyl group layers and space between them

conformational change of the head group due to the presence of water. A significantly higher value of α for DEPA reveals that the water has a larger

access to the space between the head groups arranged in a parallel packing mode.

However, the origin of differences between the two zwitterionic or nonionic surfactants, DEDA and DEPA, can be understood in terms of two forces present in their aggregates, (i) van der Waals attraction and (ii) hydration repulsion^{35,36}. At a constant temperature the hydration forces vary with the molecular conformations. For the branched hydrocarbon chains cohesive van der Waals interaction is smaller than that of the linear alkyl chains. For example, a stronger van der Waals attraction is enough to cause phase separation in a surfactant solution system. This is supported by the fact that the micelles of nonionic surfactants comprising linear alkyl chains are thought to form aggregates as the cloud point is approached. Similarly, we have shown how the addition of NaCl in the aqueous substrate increases monolayer viscosity of DETA or DEDA type of molecules⁶ by increasing cohesion amongst alkyl chains which results in the formation of solid type domains.

It is clear that our current understanding of the surfactants comprising linear and branched hydrocarbon chains is still inadequate. The main reason for this is that the roles of size and geometry and their influences on physical forces are not well understood.

Experimental

The diethanolamine (Aldrich) derivatives of (i) dodecyl and tetradecyl succinic anhydrides (DEDA) and (DETA) and (ii) polyisobutylene succinic anhydride (DEPA) of average molecular weight 500 were prepared by reacting each of the succinic anhydrides with diethanolamine at 1 : 1 molar ratio (the molecular structure is shown in Fig. 1). The dodecyl and tetradecyl succinic anhydrides were obtained from Humfry Chemicals, and the polyisobutylene succinic anhydride of average molecular weight 500 (which comprised a polyisobutylene chain of average backbone carbon number 14) was obtained from Exxon Chemicals. The ellipsometric

measurements on the monomolecular films of these surfactants at the air/water interface were simultaneously carried out along with surface pressure isotherms using a Langmuir trough combined with an ellipsometer. The surface viscosity measurements were carried out by using a Deep Channel Surface viscometer⁶. The details of the synthesis and experimental methods are described elsewhere^{4,6,18,19}.

Both for the surface pressure-area and surface viscosity-area measurements, the surfactants were spread at the air-water interface by using high purity distilled chloroform (for DETA) and hexane (for DEPA) obtained from Burdick and Jackson. A period in excess of 15 min was allowed for the solvent to evaporate. The viscosity measurements were carried out by using water, 20% (by weight) NaCl and 20% (by weight) ammonium nitrate (AN) solutions as aqueous substrates. The solutions of NaCl and AN were prepared immediately before use. The surface viscosities were measured at various concentrations of each surfactant which correspond to the range of molecular surface area for a certain surface pressure. All experiments were carried out at $20 \pm 1^\circ$.

Pure recrystallised NaCl and AN (B.D.H.) were used without any further purification. All quartz double-distilled water (Brinkman Instruments, Canada) used for the experiments was first drawn through a Millipore filtering system (Millipore Cp., Canada). The quality of aqueous sub-phase was tested prior to each run by compressing the surface without any surfactant present while noting any rise in surface pressure. The surface pressure as a function of area was obtained with an automated Langmuir trough by using a compression speed of $5 \text{ \AA}^2/\text{molecule/min}$. A teflon coated movable barrier was used for film compression. The details of the experimental procedures are mentioned in our earlier publications^{3,4}.

The interlayer spacings of liquid crystalline phases (DEDA and DEPA) were determined by low angle X-ray diffraction (Siemens Crystalloflex 4) with Ten-

nelec detector system (PSD 100). The path-length was 50 cm and the experiments were carried out in 0.7 mm capillaries with 0.01 mm walls. The measurements were made at 40 kV, 30 mA and room temperature (22.5°).

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